

Study of Iron(III), Cobalt(II), Nickel(II), Copper(II) and Manganese(II) Chelates of Vanillin-Hydrazone

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Quantitative characterisation of chelation reactions of vanillin-hydrazone (Van-hy) with Fe^{III} , Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} and Mn^{II} has been done potentiometrically in 20% aqueous ethanolic solution. Stepwise and overall proton-ligand and metal-ligand formation constants, and the thermodynamic parameters (ΔG , ΔH and ΔS) have been reported at 30° and 0.1 M (KNO_3) ionic strength. The reactions have very high values of negative enthalpy change indicating high degree of covalent character in the metal-ligand bond.

SCHIFF base hydrazides, particularly those derived from aromatic hydroxy aldehydes have been shown quite important for their pharmaceutical¹⁻⁴ and analytical^{5,6} uses. Hence, it was thought quite fruitful to study the interaction of vanillin-hydrazone (Van-hy) with certain transition metal ions, which are present in the body in traces and have profound tendency for chelation. In our earlier communication⁶ we reported the results of the physico-chemical study of the isolated complexes of Fe^{III} , Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} and Mn^{II} with van-sulphanilate. In this communication is reported the results of our study of the interaction of Van-hy with these metal ions in a 20% aqueous ethanolic solution using pH-titration technique of Irving-Rossotti⁸, at 30° and 40° and a constant ionic strength of 0.1 M with KNO_3 .

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of high purity.

Preparation and characterisation of the ligand, Van-hy, was done by the method described earlier⁷. The preparation and standardisation of the metal ion solutions and the experimental details remain the same as given elsewhere⁶.

Stoichiometry of the various species formed in solution was traced using conductometric titration, and the proton-ligand and the metal-ligand stability constants were computed by Bjerrum-Calvin pH-titration technique¹⁰ as adopted by Irving and Rossotti⁸. This involved titration of the following thermostated mixtures with a carbonate-free 0.1 M KOH, keeping ethanol-water proportion at 20% (v/v) in 50 ml, (a) 5 ml

of 0.1 M HNO_3 , (b) mixture (a) + 10 ml 0.01 M Van-hy solution, and (c) mixture (b) + 5 ml 0.002 M metal solution. The ionic strength of the solutions was maintained to 0.1 M by adding required quantity of 1.0 M KNO_3 solution. Correction for pH measurements in 20% aqueous ethanol medium was done as described by Van-Uitert and Hass¹¹ and Irving and Rossotti⁹. The pH meter readings obtained at a given alkali addition, in duplicate titrations, were reproducible with the maximum variation of 0.02 pH unit.

From the shifts in the pH titration curves of the acid, the ligand and the metal, the values of $\bar{n}A$, \bar{n} and pL^- were calculated by Irving-Rossotti equations⁸.

From $\bar{n}A$ values of the ligand at various pH values, proton-ligand stability constant, K^H for Van-hy was obtained by various computational methods, such as (i) the half-integral method, (ii) pointwise calculation method, and (iii) the linear plot method. The results obtained are recorded in Table 1 (Fig. 2) and are found in agreement.

The stepwise formation constants of the metal complexes were obtained by plotting formation curves, between the values of \bar{n} and pL^- . As the formation curves in case of these metal ions did not extend below the value of $\bar{n}=1$, hence, the value of $\log K_1$ could not be obtained from the formation curves and were obtained by the method of least squares. The values of $\log K_n$, however, were directly read from their formation curves (Fig. 3). The refined values were obtained by the best least square fit. The results obtained are given in Table 1.

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Fig. 1. Conductometric titrations, Van-hy systems. [A] Mn^{II}, [B] Co^{II}, [C] Ni^{II}, [D] Cu^{II}, and [E] Fe^{III}.

TABLE 1—STEPWISE FORMATION CONSTANTS OF VAN-HY AT 30° AND 40°, AND 0.1 M (KNO₃) IONIC STRENGTH

		30°			40°		
		Log K ₁	Log K ₂	Log β ₂	Log K ₁	Log K ₂	Log β ₂
H ⁺	(a)	7.00	—	7.00	6.60	—	6.60
	(b)	7.00	—	7.00	6.60	—	6.60
	(c)	6.80	—	6.83	6.56	—	6.46
		(7.0)*		(7.0)*	(6.60)*		(6.60)*
Fe ^{III}	(d)	8.17	4.83	13.00	7.28	4.64	11.92
Cu ^{II}	(d)	7.24	4.61	11.85	6.80	4.53	11.34
Ni ^{II}	(d)	6.14	3.43	9.57	5.73	3.35	9.08
Co ^{II}	(d)	6.13	3.40	9.53	5.72	3.35	9.07
Mn ^{II}	(d)	6.08	3.33	9.41	5.68	3.20	8.88

(a) = Half integral method, (b) = linear plot method, (c) = stepwise formation method and (d) least square method.
*Values used for calculations.

Fig. 2. Proton-ligand formation curves of Van-hy, ○ 30°, ○ 40°.

The values of stepwise and over all thermodynamic parameters (ΔG , ΔH and ΔS) accompanying the metal ligand complex forming reaction have been calculated at 30° and 0.1 M (KNO₃) ionic strength using the relations

$$\Delta G = - 2.303 RT \log K$$

$$\Delta H = - \frac{4.576 (d \log K)}{d(1/T)}$$

$$\Delta S = \frac{\Delta H - \Delta G}{T}$$

The result obtained are recorded in Table 3.

Results and Discussion

The conductometric titrations (Fig. 1) show formation of ML and ML₂ complexes between Van-hy and the metal ions used in this investigation.

TABLE 2—THERMODYNAMIC CONSTANTS OF CERTAIN TRANSITION METAL CHELATES OF VAN-HY AT 30° AND 0.1 M (KNO₃) IONIC STRENGTH

		Fe ^{III}	Cu ^{II}	Ni ^{II}	Co ^{II}	Mn ^{II}
Free energy change kcal mol ⁻¹	-ΔG ₁	11.40	10.11	8.57	8.55	8.49
	-ΔG ₂	6.74	6.43	4.79	4.74	4.65
	-ΔG	18.15	16.54	13.35	13.30	13.14
Enthalpy change kcal mol ⁻¹	-ΔH ₁	38.65	19.15	17.52	17.48	17.43
	-ΔH ₂	8.27	3.19	3.43	2.16	5.50
	-ΔH	46.95	22.25	20.95	19.64	22.84
Entropy change cal deg ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹	-ΔS ₁	-89.96	-29.85	-29.56	-29.47	29.50
	-ΔS ₂	-5.05	±10.69	±4.49	±8.52	-2.49
	-ΔS	-96.00	-19.15	-25.06	-20.94	-31.99

Fig. 3. Formation curves, Van-hy systems, 30°. [A] ○ Mn^{II}, [B] ● Ni^{II}, [C] ○ Co^{II}, [D] △ Cu^{II}, [E] □ Fe^{III}; broken lines 40°.

While, pH-titration curve, in case of the ligand showed one inflection at pH~7, with consumption of one equivalent of alkali per mole of the ligand Van-hy. This indicates one step of its acid dissociation and should involve deprotonation of the phenolic group. Further, the nature of the pH-titration curves in the absence and in the presence of the metal ions indicate that the acid dissociation (i.e. deprotonation of the phenolic group) of Van-hy is influenced by the metal ions, thus the stepwise chelation reaction of Van-hy with these metal ions may be assumed to take place through deprotonation of the phenolic group. The ratio of the successive formation constants, K_1/K_2 , are positive and show no abrupt or unusual changes indicating the normal stoichiometry for the complexes studied. Similarly, with the use of very dilute solutions ($10^{-4}M$) of the metal ions the possibility of the formation of polynuclear complexes may be ruled out.

From the analysis of the formation curves (Fig.3)

it is quite clear that the complex formation by Van-hy also follows the same sequence as was found for the amino acids^{1,2} or the Schiff bases of certain amino acids^{6,9}, that is, the formation of the two species is independent of each other.

The order of stability obtained in this study, Fe^{III}>Cu^{II}>Ni^{II} = Co^{II}>Mn^{II} shows that Van-hy also exhibits, in general, the usual relative avidities for these metal ions as shown by Van-an³, Van-sul⁶ or the amino acids¹². The values of log K_n increase on decreasing the temperature, which shows that lower temperature is favourable for the formation of complexes and for their stabilities, which also indicates the decrease in reaction rate with increase in temperature.

A perusal of the values of the thermodynamic parameters (Table 2) shows clearly that the reactions of Van-hy with these metal ions are enthalpy characterised and the values of ΔS₁, in addition to the very high values of negative enthalpy change, are also negative. The high values of negative enthalpy change indicate considerable degree of covalence in metal to ligand bond. The negative values of entropy change is an indication of the decrease in the number of particles on complex formation.

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